

Assessment of the compositional requirements to form Fe-Mn-C austenite-martensite composites

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Abstract

1 Recently, a new generation of high strength steels was introduced by utilizing a lateral chemical pattern
2 of an austenite stabilizer to create microstructures of austenite γ and martensite α' after quenching. A
3 ternary Fe-Mn-C pearlite is a suitable initial state for this if Mn effectively partitions into the cementite.
4 In the present study, two model Fe-Mn-C alloys were pearlite treated outside the well-established local
5 equilibrium, Mn partitioning regime (P-LE). A complete pearlite formation was achieved not only for
6 Fe-3.0Mn-3.0C (at.%, Alloy A) at high pearlite formation temperature but also for Fe-6.9Mn-3.2C
7 (at.%, Alloy B) at low transformation temperature. The morphology of the pearlite included fine-scaled
8 fibers and lamellae. Even though outside the P-LE region, significant Mn partitioning into cementite
9 was obtained for both alloys. Pearlite was formed at approximately the overall Mn content, while
10 growing either enriched or depleted in C for most of the reaction. The successful application of a short
11 time austenitization treatment was proven for both alloys transforming the pearlite into $\alpha' + \gamma$
12 microstructures while retaining the initial pearlite morphology. Thus, fine-structured $\alpha' + \gamma$ can be
13 synthesized from pearlite processed well outside the established Mn partitioning regimes, opening a
14 much larger compositional and processing space.

Keywords

15 Pearlite, Austenite, Martensite, Fe-Mn-C, Transformation

1 Introduction

16 In 2018, Sun et al. [1] introduced a promising processing route to achieve an outstanding combination
17 of strength and ductility in Mn containing steels by fine-scaled austenite-martensite microstructures.
18 The basic premise is to form a chemical Mn pattern in austenite γ -(Fe,Mn,C) prior to quenching. The
19 Mn pattern gets introduced via an initial pearlite formation, where Mn is strongly enriched in the
20 cementite θ -(Fe,Mn)₃C compared to the ferrite α -(Fe,Mn,C). These phases will be abbreviated as γ , θ
21 and α , respectively. In a subsequent short time austenitization (STA) treatment, the chemical Mn pattern
22 remains stable under suitable processing conditions, even after the complete transformation to γ . Rapid
23 cooling after completion of the γ transformation results in a microstructure similar in morphology and
24 dimensions to the initial pearlite, consisting of martensite α' -(Fe,Mn,C) (Mn depleted regions,
25 abbreviated with α') and austenite γ (Mn enriched regions). By additional tempering treatments,
26 remarkable ultimate tensile strength and strain to failure combinations of 1.6-2.1 GPa and 7-10 % were
27 achieved [1].

28 These results were achieved with a hypo-eutectoid alloy composition of Fe-4.3Mn-2.3C (at.%, Fe-
29 4.4Mn-0.5C in wt.%) [1]. To test the limits of this scheme, one obvious possibility would be the
30 manipulation of the alloy composition. As the final microstructure and therefore also the resulting
31 mechanical properties strongly depend on the Mn pattern, a variation of the overall Mn content would
32 be a feasible objective for tailoring the mechanical properties. However, the recent endeavors on this
33 topic [1–5], including the original work, strictly focus on Mn contents in a range of only 2-5 at.% Mn
34 and a C content that results in an overall hypo-eutectoid composition. This narrow compositional range
35 might be rationalized by what was suggested in the early work of Hutchinson et al. [6] on the growth
36 kinetics and local equilibrium (LE) conditions of Fe-Mn-C pearlite. Their work presents two different
37 design principles to predict the LE at the reaction front for pearlite formation: one for transformations
38 occurring in the three-phase region of $\alpha + \theta + \gamma$, and another for the two-phase region of $\alpha + \theta$.

39 The design principles in Ref. [6] are strictly limited by the construction of two Mn partitioning
40 boundaries that originate from a separate LE design approach for pro-eutectoid α and θ formation. The
41 approach is based on the vastly different diffusion coefficients of interstitial, fast-diffusing C compared
42 to substitutional, slow-diffusing Mn. The diffusivity ratio is about $10^4 - 10^6$ [7]. The boundaries mark
43 the compositional and temperature transition to a reaction where Mn partitioning is no longer
44 thermodynamically necessary between α/γ and θ/γ , respectively. These fundamentals have first been
45 transferred qualitatively from the pro-eutectoid reactions to pearlite formation by Coates and Hillert [7,
46 8], as the corresponding reaction front exhibits LEs for both α/γ and θ/γ . With the simultaneous
47 application of both partitioning boundaries, two major regimes were derived: (i) a partitioning regime
48 (P-LE) where the partitioning criteria with γ are fulfilled for *both* α and θ and (ii) a negligible-
49 partitioning regime (NP-LE) where the criteria are *not* satisfied for either of the two. As the pearlite
50 formation with a sufficiently strong Mn partitioning is a prerequisite for the aforementioned processing
51 route, the introduction of these regimes heavily restricts the applicable range of alloy compositions and
52 transformation temperatures, as staying inside the P-LE regime seemed reasonable [6].

53 What has not been experimentally addressed in literature thus far is the existence of an additional third
54 and fourth regime besides P-LE and NP-LE. In these regimes, only one of the two partitioning criteria
55 is fulfilled, either for α or θ . The regime of interest for this work is the one that fulfills the Mn partitioning
56 criterion for α , but not for θ . It includes a large range of temperatures and compositions, especially at
57 higher Mn and C contents, which have yet to be tested for Mn partitioning and the possibility to apply
58 the intended STA processing. However, with increasing Mn content the eutectoid line as well as the

59 three-phase field that separates the γ single-phase field and the $\alpha + \theta$ two-phase field, shift to lower
60 temperatures [9]. A lower transformation temperature as well as high contents of the slow-diffusing Mn
61 will result in a currently unknown retardation of the pearlite transformation. Another aspect that needs
62 to be considered at such retarded reaction velocities is the formation of metastable phases or other
63 microstructures besides $\alpha + \theta$ pearlite. In case of Fe-Mn-C, potential formation of M_5C_2 [10] and $M_{23}C_6$
64 carbides needs to be considered, with M representing metallic elements. Their formation has been
65 reported for example in Cr-rich and Al-rich, Mn-containing steels [10, 11].

66 Thus, the following research questions will be addressed in the present study:

- 67 1. Does a pearlite treatment for a low Mn containing Fe-3.0Mn-3.0C (at.%) at 600 °C and for a
68 high Mn containing Fe-6.9Mn-3.2C (at.%) at 540 °C result in an entirely transformed
69 microstructure comprising pearlite that only consists of α and θ ?
- 70 2. Does pearlite in these Fe-Mn-C alloys exhibit considerable Mn partitioning into θ and how does
71 it compare to global equilibrium (GE) and LE conditions?
- 72 3. Is it possible to achieve a $\alpha' + \gamma$ microstructure by short-time austenitization from these pearlite
73 conditions?

2 Experiments and Simulations

74 The design of the Mn partitioning boundaries was first developed for pro-eutectoid α and θ formation [7,
75 12] and quantitatively applied to Fe-Mn-C pearlite formation by Hutchinson et al. [6]. Their application
76 for given isothermal sections is shown in Fig. 1. It divides the parameter space, described by X_C and
77 X_{Mn} as the molar fraction of C and Mn, respectively, into four regions. The representation in Fig. 1,
78 however is given by using the derived quantities $U_C = X_C/(1 - X_C)$ and $U_{Mn} = X_{Mn}/(1 - X_C)$
79 according to the treatment by Hillert [8, 12] as well as Coates [7] and Hutchinson [6]. A detailed
80 explanation of the physical meaning and practical usage of these variables can be found in the
81 Supplementary Material of this article. The temperatures of 600 (Fig. 1 a)) and 540 °C (Fig. 1 b)) were
82 selected to capture a potentially fast transformation at low Mn contents and a retarded one at high Mn
83 contents, respectively. The design of the partitioning boundaries (dot-dashed, purple lines in Fig. 1) are
84 adopted from Ref. [7] and comprehensively described for the present cases in the Supplementary
85 Material, Fig. S1. The thermodynamic data was obtained using the 2023 PanHEA database in the Pandat
86 software provided by CompuTherm (USA). The theoretical data on the phase field positions of the Fe-
87 Mn-C system are in good agreement with experimental literature data in the relevant compositional
88 range [1, 9, 13–21]. All additional thermodynamic LE considerations that are not captured by Pandat
89 were obtained using self-developed Matlab scripts which are published public domain [22].

90 As mentioned in Sec. 1, out of the four regimes formed by the use of the two partitioning boundaries,
91 only two have been addressed in literature thus far [6–8]: The P-LE regime (highlighted in purple) and
92 the NP-LE regime (highlighted in gray). For the pearlite transformation, these two regimes are uniquely
93 defined by the fulfillment of the two independent Mn partitioning criteria between α and γ as well as θ
94 and γ (see Supplementary Material Fig. S1).

95 The regime to the right of the intersection of the two dot-dashed purple lines in Figs. 1 a) and b) is the
96 scope of the present article. It includes high overall Mn contents which hold the potential of stabilizing
97 large fractions of γ in the final microstructure after STA. Here, the partitioning criteria are fulfilled for
98 α , but not for θ formation.

99 Inside this regime two model alloys, Alloy A and Alloy B, were selected. They lie inside the $\alpha + \theta$ two-
100 phase field as well as inside the metastable extensions of the $\alpha + \gamma$ and $\gamma + \theta$ phase field boundaries to

101 avoid pro-eutectoid α or θ formation. The nominal compositions of the Mn-lean Alloy A and the Mn-
 102 rich Alloy B are Fe-3.0Mn-3.0C and Fe-6.9Mn-3.2C (at.%, Fe-3.0Mn-0.7C and Fe-7.0Mn-0.7C in
 103 wt.%), respectively.

Fig. 1: Fe-Mn-C isothermal sections at a) 600 °C and b) 540 °C. Black bold lines illustrate the phase fields in GE. Black dotted lines indicate the metastable extrapolations of the $\alpha + \gamma$ and $\gamma + \theta$ phase field boundaries. The purple dot-dashed lines represent Mn partitioning boundaries for α (near horizontal) and θ (near vertical). P-LE and NP-LE regions are marked purple and gray, respectively. Alloys A and B, both lie outside these regions. The experimentally determined compositions listed in Tabs. 1 and 2 are displayed.

104 Alloy manufacturing was done by arc melting high purity bulk elements as well as an in-house
 105 synthesized Fe_3C obtained by the same method. The elements Mn (etched nominal purity 99.8 %) and
 106 graphite (nominal purity 99.999 %) were provided by chemPUR GmbH (Germany). Fe (nominal purity
 107 99.99 %) was provided by Alfa Aesar (United States). Arc melting was conducted in an AM/0.5 furnace
 108 provided by Edmund Bühler GmbH (Germany). The furnace chamber was evacuated to $5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mbar
 109 and filled with Ar. This process was repeated for three times in total in order to purify the melting
 110 atmosphere. Then, a vacuum of less than $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mbar was established. The processing chamber was
 111 then filled with Ar once more to a pressure of 600 mbar. Residual O_2 within the furnace chamber was
 112 gettered by liquefying a Zr granule before melting the bulk elements. Every manufactured ingot was
 113 flipped and re-melted at least five times. The alloy ingots were homogenized utilizing a STF15/450 21-
 114 601449 tube furnace by Carbolite Gero GmbH & Co. KG (Germany) with flowing high purity Ar
 115 atmosphere. The heat treatment temperature was 1100 °C for a dwell time of 96 h. Heating and cooling
 116 were conducted at a rate of 115 K/h. The chemical composition was determined through optical emission
 117 spectroscopy (OES) by analyzing both, the top and bottom side after the last re-melting step. The results
 118 are displayed in Tabs. 1 and 2 for Alloys A and B, respectively. The standard deviation for all elements
 119 was determined to be < 0.07 at.% (0.07 wt.%). Samples for further investigations were cut from the
 120 alloy batches using a high-speed rotatory cutting device (Struers, France).

121 Pearlite formation was carried out in air at atmospheric pressure using two pre-heated box furnaces.
 122 After completion of the prior austenitization step at 910 °C for 1 h, an immediate furnace transfer was
 123 performed. Pearlite in Alloy A and Alloy B was formed at 600 °C for 16 h and 540 °C for 96 h,
 124 respectively, based on initial trials to obtain relevant temperature/time combinations. The heat
 125 treatments were concluded by oil quenching.

126 The STA treatments were done in a pre-heated box furnace at 770 °C for 150 s and also concluded by
 127 oil quenching. To ensure a high heating rate, the samples were covered by pre-heated Al_2O_3 powder at
 128 the start of the treatment.

129 The samples for microstructure characterization were prepared by water-cooled grinding with SiC paper
130 followed by standard metallographic polishing steps with 3 and 1 μm polycrystalline diamond
131 suspensions. As a finishing step, polishing with MasterMet-2 by Buehler (USA) was performed for
132 5 min. Samples were subsequently etched in a 1 % Nital solution for 5 s. The grinding process was
133 carried out to remove any decarburized layer that has formed during the heat treatments. Microstructure
134 characterization was performed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). For secondary electron (SEM-
135 SE) as well as backscattered electron (SEM-BSE) contrast imaging, a Leo Gemini 1530 field-emission
136 SEM by Zeiss (Germany) was utilized. Low magnification, wide field of view micrographs with high
137 resolution were obtained by automated stitching in Microsoft Image Composite Editor. The
138 quantification of microstructural details including the area fractions of the constituting phases and
139 morphologies was carried out using the ImageJ software. Estimates for the fractions of regions of similar
140 morphology were done by manually selecting and asserting regions with θ aspect ratios close to one as
141 fibrous. Fibers oriented parallel to the sample surface were therefore identified as lamellae. Micrographs
142 for all analysis were selected randomly and at different magnification to enable both a large overall area
143 of investigation as well as high accuracy of the imaging. The difference in total area mapped between
144 different magnification micrographs was considered. The determined area fractions were converted into
145 volume fractions under the assumption of isometry and isotropy. A more detailed assessment of
146 parameters like θ spacing or θ morphology fraction would require 3D methods for microstructure
147 analysis, e.g. FIB tomography, and was not scope of the present study.

148 Phase identification was done by means of transmission synchrotron X-ray diffraction (XRD) at
149 beamline BL13XU, SPring-8 of the Japan Synchrotron Radiation Research Institute (JASRI). The
150 diffraction experiments were performed using monochromatic synchrotron radiation at an energy of
151 30 keV ($\lambda = 0.0413$ nm) and 30 s exposure time. The calibration of the 2θ zero-shift and sample
152 displacement was done with a standard specimen of ceria (CeO_2). Additionally, local analysis of the
153 constituting phases was performed via selected area electron diffraction (TEM-SAED) with a JEM-
154 2100F by Jeol (Japan) and a Titan3 by FEI (USA) transmission electron microscope (TEM) operated at
155 200 kV and 300 kV, respectively. For determining the local composition of the phases, both energy
156 dispersive X-ray spectroscopy in scanning TEM (STEM-EDS) as well as atom probe tomography (APT)
157 were considered. However, due to significant inaccuracies introduced by quantifying the C content, APT
158 was selected as the superior method both in terms of data accuracy and spatial resolution [23]. The
159 experiments were performed on both alloys after pearlite formation with a LEAP 4000X HR by Cameca
160 (France). Data presented in the main article were generated in voltage mode, while additional data
161 depicted in the Supplementary Material were generated in laser mode. Tip preparation was done via
162 focused ion beam (FIB) milling with an Auriga 60 by Zeiss (Germany). Tips presented in the
163 Supplementary Material were coated with Cr to increase tip stability, following the routine used in
164 Ref. [24]. Peak decomposition was required for the θ regions, which was applied by the integrated
165 feature of the AP Suite 6.3 software (Cameca, France). The software decomposes overlapping peaks by
166 considering the remaining unique peak(s) of the species of interest of the same charge and applies the
167 relative natural abundances to weigh the contribution of that species to the initial peak. An example for
168 this would be C_2^{1+} and C_4^{2+} in θ . Both species exhibit peaks at 24 and 25 Da. However, C_4^{2+} possesses a
169 unique peak at 24.5 Da as well. Considering the natural abundances of the different C_4^{2+} isotopes, the
170 contribution to the peak at 24 Da and 25 Da can be derived, which leaves the remaining counts of the
171 peaks for C_2^{1+} .

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Pearlite Formation

172 To answer the research questions from Sec. 1, it is essential to develop an understanding of the
 173 intricacies of a complete Fe-Mn-C pearlite formation and the Mn partitioning behavior. Hillert [12]
 174 proposed that for simultaneous Mn and C partitioning, the driving force for C diffusion in γ ahead of the
 175 reaction front must be reduced to compensate for the orders of magnitude difference in diffusion
 176 coefficients of the elements. A practical way to achieve this condition was shown by Hutchinson
 177 et al. [6], i.e. γ in contact with either growing θ or α are required to share the same C activity a_C^γ . This
 178 can be elegantly applied quantitatively to isothermal sections of the ternary phase diagram, as depicted
 179 in Fig. 2. The compositions of γ ahead of growing θ and α are located on the same C iso-activity line in
 180 Fig. 2 (blue dots on the C iso-activity line at the intersections with the dotted, metastable extensions).
 181 The forming θ and α are obtained from following the tie lines (blue, solid lines) connected to these γ
 182 compositions. As Hutchinson et al. [6] obtained a steady-state growth of pearlite within the $\alpha + \theta$ two-
 183 phase field with constant growth rate and interphase spacing, an additional boundary condition regarding
 184 the overall composition of the growing pearlite was introduced. Namely, its composition must be
 185 consistent with the alloy composition. This can only be achieved when the connecting line (blue, dashed
 186 line) between the growing θ and α intersects the alloy composition. This connecting line does not
 187 represent a tie line as the two growing phases are not in equilibrium with each other. In what follows,
 188 this design principle is referred to as steady-state, C activity-based local equilibrium condition (SCA-
 189 LE). As depicted in Fig. 2, the application of the SCA-LE design indicates an enrichment of Mn in θ
 190 during pearlite formation even though it is being applied to Alloys A and B outside the P-LE regime.

Fig. 2: Schematic design according to SCA-LE in isothermal sections: a) Alloy A at 600 °C and b) Alloy B at 540 °C. The illustration of the isothermal section is the same as for Fig. 1. The blue solid lines indicate tie lines while the blue dashed line is the line connecting θ and α forming during steady-state pearlite growth. The predicted enrichment of Mn in θ is: a) 8.0 at.% (vs. 2.8 at.% in Alloy A) and b) 35.0 at.% (vs. 6.9 at.% in Alloy B).

191 In Fig. 3, micrographs of both alloys are shown after their respective pearlite treatments: 600 °C/16 h
 192 for Alloy A and 540 °C/96 h for Alloy B. A complete transformation was achieved for both alloys. High
 193 resolution, wide field of view micrographs obtained from stitching proving the statement are provided
 194 via a public repository [25]. Despite the lower transformation temperature, which is usually associated
 195 with a decrease in lamellar spacing [26], Alloy B does not show a clearly refined microstructure
 196 compared to Alloy A. With respect to pearlite morphology, a notable difference between the two alloys
 197 is obtained. Both exhibit extended regions of fibrous morphology, comprising a volume fraction of
 198 (0.91 ± 0.08) and (0.32 ± 0.12) of the pearlite in Alloys A and B, respectively. The volume-specific
 199 phase fraction of θ is (0.06 ± 0.01) for Alloy A and (0.21 ± 0.02) for Alloy B. Alloy B frequently

200 exhibits regions of increasing interface spacing towards the colony boundaries, thus, at potentially late
 201 stages of the transformation before completion. Due to their low overall fraction of (0.02 ± 0.01) , these
 202 regions were not included in the randomly selected micrographs to determine the volume-specific phase
 203 fractions.

Fig. 3: SEM-SE micrographs (Nital etching) after completion of pearlite formation: a) Alloy A, 600 °C/16 h and b) Alloy B, 540 °C/96 h. No untransformed regions were found. θ appears light, α appears dark. Lamellar morphology is indicated by yellow, fibrous by red arrows. High resolution, wide field of view micrographs obtained from stitching are available via Ref. [25].

204 To identify the constituting phases of both alloys after the pearlite treatment, transmission XRD
 205 experiments were performed. Due to large pearlite colony size, preferred orientation and intensities
 206 different from powder diffraction patterns were obtained. All analyzed peaks were exclusively attributed
 207 to either α or θ , as shown in Fig. 4 and no evidence for any other carbide than θ or untransformed γ was
 208 found. The $(211)_\theta$ and $(112)_\theta$ peaks were considered to uniquely identify the carbide as θ .

Fig. 4: Transmission XRD patterns of: a) Alloy A and b) Alloy B. The intensity is plotted as a function of 2θ . Characteristic diffraction peaks corresponding to α are marked in red, while peaks associated with θ are highlighted in blue. All relevant peaks of θ are highlighted below the spectra, while the $(211)_\theta$ and $(112)_\theta$ peaks were used to uniquely identify the carbide

209 Further characterization of the pearlite was done via TEM imaging and electron diffraction. Due to the
 210 large pearlite colony size, TEM specimens were taken from representative regions, i.e. a fibrous colony
 211 for Alloy A and a lamellar colony for Alloy B. Both lift outs were taken in regions of near constant
 212 interface spacing (73 ± 26 nm) and (104 ± 19 nm), respectively. Bright field micrographs as well as the
 213 TEM-SAED patterns are shown in Fig. 4. The zone axes in both Fig. 4 a) and d) are parallel to the
 214 $[100]_\theta$ direction following the lattice parameter convention, $b > a > c$ for θ . The lift outs were
 215 chosen perpendicular to the long fiber axes for Alloy A (Fig. 4 a)) and the lamellar plane for Alloy B

216 (Fig. 4 c)). In such a scenario, fibrous and lamellar colonies of interest cannot be distinguished from one
 217 another as both appear similar at the sample surface. They can only be distinguished after cutting a FIB
 218 trench and subsequent cross-sectional imaging. For both samples, the transmission XRD results
 219 regarding the constituting α and θ phases were confirmed by TEM-SAED patterns in Figs. 4 b) and d),
 220 respectively. Furthermore, the orientation relationship (OR) was determined. The investigated colonies
 221 of Alloy A and Alloy B both exhibit variants of the Isaichev OR with $\langle 111 \rangle_{\alpha} \parallel \langle 100 \rangle_{\theta}$ and
 222 $\{1\bar{2}1\}_{\alpha} \parallel \{011\}_{\theta}$, which is well established for pearlite [27]. Please note that Fig. 4 a) for Alloy A
 223 exhibits a twin site of the OR with a $(01\bar{1})_{\theta}$ habit plane instead of $(011)_{\theta}$ as for Fig. 4 b). The θ twin
 224 variant is of compound character with the habit plane $(011)_{\theta}$, shear direction $[01\bar{1}]_{\theta}$ and shear plane
 225 $(100)_{\theta}$. Furthermore, the twin orientation can be achieved via a rotation of the θ matrix crystal around
 226 the $[100]_{\theta}$ direction by 111.8° . This equates to the angle between $(011)_{\theta}$ and $(01\bar{1})_{\theta}$ in the θ unit cell.
 227 The Isaichev OR might alternatively be expressed differently by defining the habit plane according to
 228 $\{0\bar{1}1\}_{\alpha} \parallel \{031\}_{\theta}$. This can be attributed to the very small angular mismatch (0.3°) between the sets of
 229 lattice planes involved. However, the angular mismatch becomes more apparent for high indexed spots.

Fig. 5: TEM bright field micrographs (a,c)) and corresponding TEM-SAED patterns (b, d)) of: a), b) fibrous regions from Alloy A and c),d) lamellar region from Alloy B. The zone axes (ZA) in both b) and d) are $[111]_{\alpha} \parallel [100]_{\theta}$.

230 Samples for APT were selected in similar fashion like the TEM specimens, i.e., lift out via FIB in a
 231 fibrous colony for Alloy A and in a lamellar colony for Alloy B, both within regions of nearly constant
 232 interface spacing. In total, four tips were analyzed with two for Alloy A stemming from the same colony
 233 and two for Alloy B from different colonies. One of each alloy is discussed as an example. The
 234 remaining data agrees with the statements and discussion. The data is included in Fig. S2, Fig. S3 and
 235 Tab. S2 of the Supplementary Material. To allow for a more detailed assessment of the chemical
 236 composition, the local phase fractions were determined at the lift out position from SEM-SE
 237 micrographs. The local θ volume fraction of Alloy A is 0.05, while it is 0.19 for Alloy B. These values
 238 were then converted to the local molar phase fractions f_m which are provided together with the values
 239 for α in Tabs. 1 and 2 for Alloys A and B, respectively.

Tab. 1: Compositions X , C activity in γ a_C^γ , molar phase fractions f_m and U of Alloy A according to thermodynamic calculations (GE, SCA-LE), experimental (exp.) results from APT analyses and reconstructions. $^+$ denotes experimental data. $^\#$ denotes experimental data adjusted according to the thermodynamic dataset. The other data was derived from the thermodynamic dataset.

Condition	Phase	Position	X_C	X_{Mn}	U_C	U_{Mn}	a_C^γ	f_m	
Alloy A	–	–	0.029 ⁺	0.028 ⁺	0.030	0.029	–	–	
GE	α	–	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.011	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.011	–	0.88	
	θ	–	0.250	0.163	0.333	0.217	–	0.12	
SCA-LE	α	γ	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.021	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.021	–	0.88	
	θ	γ	0.250	0.080	0.333	0.106	–	0.12	
	γ	α		0.031	0.114	0.032	0.118	0.29	–
		θ		0.020	0.027	0.020	0.027	0.29	–
Exp.	α	–	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ ⁺	0.020 ⁺	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.020	–	0.95 ⁺	
	θ	–	0.262 ⁺	0.218 ⁺	0.355	0.295	–	0.05 ⁺	
Reconstr.	α	γ	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ ⁺	0.020 ⁺	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.020	–	0.95 ⁺	
	θ	γ	0.250 [#]	0.222 [#]	0.333	0.296	–	0.05 ⁺	
	γ	α		0.034	0.111	0.035	0.115	0.33	–
		θ		0.017	0.089	0.017	0.091	0.16	–

Tab. 2: Compositions X , C activity in γ a_C^γ , molar phase fractions f_m and U of Alloy B according to thermodynamic calculations (GE, SCA-LE), experimental (exp.) results from APT analyses and reconstructions. $^+$ denotes experimental data. $^\#$ denotes experimental data adjusted according to the thermodynamic dataset. The other data was derived from the thermodynamic dataset.

Condition	Phase	Position	X_C	X_{Mn}	U_C	U_{Mn}	a_C^γ	f_m	
Alloy B	–	–	0.029 ⁺	0.069 ⁺	0.030	0.071	–	–	
GE	α	–	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.029	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.029	–	0.88	
	θ	–	0.250	0.375	0.333	0.500	–	0.12	
SCA-LE	α	γ	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.032	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.032	–	0.88	
	θ	γ	0.250	0.350	0.333	0.466	–	0.12	
	γ	α		0.013	0.179	0.013	0.181	0.09	–
		θ		0.010	0.147	0.010	0.148	0.09	–
Exp.	α	–	$2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ ⁺	0.020 ⁺	$2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.020	–	0.80 ⁺	
	θ	–	0.221 ⁺	0.293 ⁺	0.284	0.376	–	0.20 ⁺	
Reconstr.	α	γ	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ [#]	0.020 ⁺	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.020	–	0.80 ⁺	
	θ	γ	0.250 [#]	0.282 [#]	0.333	0.376	–	0.20 ⁺	
	γ	α		0.054	0.158	0.058	0.167	0.76	–
		θ		0.011	0.106	0.011	0.107	0.14	–

240 Two reconstructed tips are depicted in Fig. 6. Both show Mn and C enrichment coinciding in the same
241 same region, a θ fiber (Fig. 6 a)) for Alloy A and lamella (Fig. 6 b)) for Alloy B. The determined C content
242 of θ in all tips (Tab. 1, Tab. 2 and Tab. S2 in the Supplementary Material) deviates from the
243 stoichiometric expectation, which may be explained by different phenomena. Possible scenarios are
244 discussed in Ref. [28, 29]. An additional aspect that could have affected the evaporation and, therefore,

245 quantification of C is the difference in θ morphology. However, as the focus of this work is the Mn
246 partitioning, this matter is not discussed further here.

247 While Alloy A shows a Mn content of 21.8 at.% (vs. 2.8 at.% in the alloy) within θ , Alloy B exhibits
248 29.3 at.% of Mn (vs. 6.9 at.% in the alloy). Thus, Mn partitioning takes place during the pearlite reaction
249 for both alloys, regardless of being located outside the P-LE region in the isothermal sections of Fig. 1.
250 A more detailed overview of the local chemical compositions, including the C contents, are shown in
251 Tabs. 1 and 2 for Alloys A and B, respectively. The interface between α and θ was investigated for
252 potential element segregation. Considering the spatial resolution limit of roughly 2 nm [23], all tips
253 indicate practically sharp interfaces with no detectable segregation. The concentration profiles that were
254 used for the analysis are shown in the Supplementary Material, Fig. S3 a), c) for the tips discussed in
255 the main article and b), d) for the additional ones.

Fig. 6: Reconstructed APT tip of: a) Alloy A with a θ fiber and b) Alloy B with a θ lamella. Fe is represented in red, Mn in blue and C in orange. The fiber and lamella are enriched in C and Mn. For α , the volume that was used to determine the chemical composition is illustrated via the black boxes. For θ , the analyzed volume was selected inside a Mn iso surface to avoid the effect of interphase regions.

3.2 Local Equilibrium Models and Reaction Kinetics

256 The results presented in Sec. 3.1 show that pearlite formation can lead to significant Mn partitioning
257 even when formed outside the P-LE regime. The P-LE and NP-LE regimes result directly from the Mn
258 partitioning boundary lines for pro-eutectoid α and θ formation, see Fig. 1. These boundary lines
259 originate from the LE design of the two reactions and describe the thermodynamic requirements of
260 partitioning between α/γ and θ/γ , respectively. Taking pro-eutectoid α formation as an example: For
261 each composition on the α partitioning boundary line, the LE predicts the same U_{Mn} within the forming
262 α and the bulk γ . The forming α can thus dissolve the overall Mn content within the alloy, making Mn
263 partitioning thermodynamically unnecessary. This condition is met for all compositions below this
264 partitioning boundary for a given isothermal section (NP-LE for α formation). In case of pro-eutectoid
265 θ formation, the same holds true for all compositions to the right of the boundary (NP-LE for θ
266 formation). Hence, composition and temperature should be selected to lie in the respective P-LE regime
267 if Mn partitioning is to be guaranteed during the reaction.

268 For pearlite formation, where both partitioning boundaries are applied simultaneously, a similar
269 argumentation is possible. This can be attributed to the fact that during the transformation, the forming
270 α and θ are in contact with γ at the reaction front and are therefore expected to form two independent
271 LEs between α/γ and θ/γ , respectively. In the case of pro-eutectoid reactions, the rate controlling
272 diffusion occurs perpendicular to the reaction front. Pearlite formation, however, is controlled by lateral
273 diffusion processes along or through the interfaces of the reaction front, i.e. from the γ ahead of the

274 growing α to the γ ahead of the growing θ . For a complete pearlite transformation ($\gamma \rightarrow \alpha + \theta$ in the two-
275 phase field), elemental partitioning associated with the LE at the reaction front must be accommodated
276 entirely by the product phases α and θ . Hence, it is reasonable to assume that already fulfilling a single
277 partitioning criterion for pearlite formation inside the two-phase field is sufficient to eventually achieve
278 Mn partitioning between α and θ . In the present study, this is shown for the interesting region where the
279 Mn partitioning criterion is fulfilled only for α .

280 Hutchinson et al. [6] experimentally validated predicted pearlite compositions via STEM-EDS. In the
281 present work, APT was chosen as it allows an increased quantification accuracy for both C and Mn [23].
282 To re-evaluate the viability of the SCA-LE method, its main design principles are compared to the
283 experimental data of Alloys A and B in the following. It is assumed that the experimentally determined
284 compositions of α and θ (Tabs. 1 and 2 for Alloys A and B, respectively) correspond to their
285 compositions during the reaction right after the reaction front has passed the region of interest. This
286 assumption is based on the findings of Hutchinson et al. [6]. They determined the Mn content in
287 partitioned Fe-Mn-C pearlite as a function of distance from the reaction front for a given transformation
288 condition. In addition, pearlite colonies were analyzed at different stages of the transformation, i.e. after
289 different hold times at the respective pearlite formation temperature. Both analyses suggest that when
290 pearlite formation is performed in the two phase field, the chemical composition of a specific region
291 within a sample remains near constant even after extended hold times [6]. Since the pearlite treatment
292 was terminated shortly after the complete transformation, a comparison between the SCA-LE model and
293 post-transformation experimental LE data is viable. The APT data of the two product phases allows for
294 a reconstruction of the γ/α and γ/θ tie lines, as each composition of the product phases may only be
295 described by a single tie line. The validation will focus on whether the reconstructed tie line end points
296 for the γ/α and γ/θ interfaces share the same C iso-activity and whether the connecting line between the
297 α and θ compositions intersects the overall alloy composition.

298 For the γ/θ tie line reconstruction, the C content within the θ was set to 25.0 at.%. This was done via a
299 count correction of the C ions and therefore the total amount of ions that were included in the APT
300 analysis of θ . The resulting Mn content was then deliberately equipped with a conservative uncertainty
301 of ± 3.0 at.% to account for any inaccuracy introduced by the quantification of C. The α composition
302 was not changed, however, as the determined composition does not lie exactly on the respective
303 metastable phase field extension, the reconstructed γ/α tie line slightly differs in its α composition. Fig. 7
304 shows the reconstructed tie lines as well as the connecting line for Alloys A and B in Figs. 7 a) and b),
305 respectively. The compositions of all phases at the respective interfaces, as well as the C activities in γ
306 a_C^γ are appended to Tabs. 1 and 2 as the reconstructed data. To further assist with the analysis, the GE
307 condition that might be achieved after an infinitely long hold time is also given in Tabs. 1 and 2 for both
308 alloys.

Fig. 7: Fe-Mn-C isotherms at: a) 600 °C and b) 540 °C. The active tie lines (orange, full) as well as the line connecting (orange, dashed) the α and θ compositions are shown. The applied uncertainty for the composition of θ impacts both the position of the connecting line as well as the γ/θ tie line. The possible positions of the connecting line are indicated by an orange box. For the endpoints of the γ/θ tie line, the possible range is indicated by black arrows and open data points (orange). Alloys A and B both lie considerably off the connecting line.

309 Considering Tabs. 1 and 2, the γ s in contact with α and θ do not share the same C activity for the two
 310 alloys. This remains true even when a conservative uncertainty of the θ composition is considered.

311 Furthermore, the connecting line between α and θ does not intersect the alloy composition for both
 312 alloys. Such a scenario is only possible if the composition of the forming pearlite does not correspond
 313 to the overall composition of the alloy, i.e., the reaction does not meet steady-state conditions.
 314 Hutchinson et al. [6] already noted this and included such a possibility when introducing the SCA-LE
 315 model. As the C iso-activity line, which determines the local equilibria at the reaction front in SCA-LE,
 316 is not required to intersect the alloy composition, C diffusion between γ at the interface and the bulk is
 317 possible (when a difference in C activity exists). Despite this, the transformation follows apparent
 318 steady-state conditions for most of the duration, with a near constant interface velocity and interface
 319 spacing [6]. This growth continues until the change in C content within the diminishing γ becomes so
 320 drastic that an abrupt change in growth is required. In Fe-Mn-C pearlite, this may be expressed by a
 321 sudden increase or decrease in the interface spacing of the θ [6]. One aspect that must be mentioned in
 322 this context is that spacing alone is insufficient to describe this phenomenon. As C solubility in α and θ
 323 is either extremely small or at a stoichiometric 25 at.%, a drastic change in C content in the γ near the
 324 reaction front can only be accommodated by a shift in the product phase fractions. Additionally, an
 325 increase or decrease in interphase spacing may be observed.

326 For the two cases depicted in Fig. 2, SCA-LE predicts that the activities in bulk γ are higher than in the
 327 near-interface γ . Thus, a diffusion flux of C towards the interface would be possible during most of the
 328 growth for both alloys, potentially depleting the bulk γ in C. In contrast, the reconstructions of the
 329 experimental results indicate that the C activity in γ ahead of the growing α is larger than that ahead of
 330 θ , while the C activity of the bulk γ is larger than both for Alloy A and in between the two for Alloy B.
 331 To further investigate any possible bulk diffusion during the reaction, analyzing the local chemical
 332 composition of the product pearlite is a viable method. Of interest is the deviation of both the Mn and C
 333 content between the pearlite and the bulk γ , which is equal to the overall alloy composition for a large
 334 part of the reaction.

335 To determine the local composition of pearlite, both the reconstructed chemical composition as well as
 336 the phase fractions of the product phases are necessary and summarized for Alloys A and B in Tabs. 1
 337 and 2, respectively. This allows for the actual composition of the pearlite to be calculated, following

338

$$\begin{pmatrix} X_C \\ X_{Mn} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} X_C^\alpha & X_C^\theta \\ X_{Mn}^\alpha & X_{Mn}^\theta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} f_m^\alpha \\ f_m^\theta \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

339 Here, X_Y represents the total molar fraction of the element Y within the pearlite in the region of interest,
 340 X_Y^Z is the molar fraction of Y in phase Z and f_m^Z is the molar fraction of phase Z . For Alloy A, the local
 341 composition of the pearlite is $X_C = 1.3$ at.% and $X_{Mn} = (3.0 \pm 0.2)$ at.% (vs. 2.9 at.% C and 2.8 at.% Mn
 342 in the alloy) and for Alloy B $X_C = 5.0$ at.% and $X_{Mn} = (7.2 \pm 0.6)$ at.% (vs. 2.9 at.% C and 6.9 at.% Mn
 343 in the alloy). For both cases, pearlite resembles the Mn content of the bulk γ (alloy composition), but
 344 not the C content. In the case of Alloy A, γ would become enriched in C during growth, while the C
 345 content in γ would have decreased in Alloy B. However, characteristic features in the microstructure
 346 suggesting such varying growth conditions were only observed in Alloy B. Here, depending on the
 347 orientation of the pearlite colonies to the surface, an increase in the lamellar spacing and a reduction in
 348 the θ fraction was observed. In Alloy A, no features corresponding to C enrichment of γ during growth
 349 were found. The reason for this is most likely the heterogeneity of the predominantly fibrous
 350 microstructure as the longitudinal axis of the fiber must be oriented parallel to the sample surface to
 351 clearly observe changes in spacing and phase fraction during growth.

352 These results were not consistently predicted by considering the C activity values of the SCA-LE
 353 method. The same holds true for the experimentally reconstructed SCA-LE data. Considering the
 354 deviation of the LE model from the present experimental data, SCA-LE in its current form does not
 355 seem suitable for accurate predictions in the investigated parameter space, ranging from 3 wt.% Mn and
 356 600 °C transformation temperature to 7 wt.% and 540 °C, respectively. In addition to the underlying
 357 diffusion problem of simultaneous Mn and C partitioning, modelling pearlite formation in the two-phase
 358 field specifically requires the consideration of two more aspects. The first one is the *apparent* steady-
 359 state character of the transformation. SCA-LE was developed with the goal of modelling a steady-state
 360 reaction [6]. This decision is based on the two steady-state features of the reaction, namely the near
 361 constant growth rate and interface spacing (for most of the reaction). However, while appearing as
 362 steady-state in this regard, the reaction most likely exhibits constant bulk C diffusion to or away from
 363 the reaction front for a large set of parameters. While SCA-LE addresses the constant volume fraction
 364 during growth by the design of the connecting line intersecting the alloy composition, the C activity
 365 difference between interphase and bulk γ in most cases will violate steady-state requirements as a
 366 constant diffusion flux is enforced. Another aspect is the occurrence of different θ morphologies, which
 367 are a prominent feature in the present alloys but rarely addressed in literature. The difference in curvature
 368 of fibrous and lamellar θ at the reaction front might be too large to be neglected and might affect the
 369 LEs. In summary, a more precise LE model could be developed if adequate considerations of the
 370 (quasi-)steady-state conditions and the interphase curvature at the reaction front are incorporated.

3.3 Short Time Austenitization

371 Apart from the theoretical models to describe the Fe-Mn-C pearlite reaction, the APT results clearly
 372 show a significant Mn partitioning between α and θ for both alloys. In order to validate if the respective
 373 Mn pattern is sufficient for the promising scheme introduced by Sun et al. [1], an STA treatment was
 374 performed. A successful STA treatment is considered an independent, statistically relevant proof of Mn
 375 partitioning, as the lamellar/fibrous $\alpha' + \gamma$ microstructure cannot be synthesized without it. The heat
 376 treatment was conducted at 770 °C for 150 s for both alloys and was concluded via oil quenching.
 377 Micrographs after the treatment can be seen in Figs. 7 a) and b) for Alloys A and B, respectively. For
 378 the given set of parameters, a complete transformation to γ was observed. The novel $\alpha' + \gamma$
 379 microstructure can be easily distinguished from the initial pearlite as there is a contrast inversion in both

380 SEM-SE and SEM-BSE contrast. While in pearlite the minority phase θ appears bright, the minority
 381 phase γ appears dark. Both alloys largely retained their morphology when compared to the initial
 382 pearlite, i.e. both still show fibrous (highlighted by red arrows in Fig. 8 a)) as well as lamellar
 383 (highlighted by yellow arrows in Fig. 8) domains. However, both alloys also show regions with no
 384 distinct morphology (highlighted by blue arrows in Fig. 8). After a region was transformed to γ , any
 385 additional hold time can be considered as a homogenization, where the Mn pattern gradually dissolves.
 386 The process is expected to be fastest in regions of small lamellar spacing, as well as weak Mn pattern.
 387 A significant local Mn homogenization may therefore be achieved already during the transformation to
 388 γ . For a given pearlitic sample, this can be partially or completely avoided by choosing the STA
 389 temperature sufficiently high to allow for a fast transformation. An STA temperature only slightly above
 390 A_3/A_{CM} (C and Mn dependent lower temperature limits, at which α / θ will be entirely transformed to γ)
 391 may result in a slow transformation, which allows already transformed regions to be homogenized
 392 before the microstructure is entirely austenitic. Substantially homogenized regions are unable to retain
 393 the aspired morphology, as the peak Mn content is insufficient to stabilize γ .

Fig. 8: a) and b) show micrographs of Alloys A and B using SEM-BSE (Nital etching) contrast after the STA treatment, respectively. No untransformed regions were observed for either alloy. Dark regions are γ , while medium gray regions are α' . Lamellar morphology is marked by yellow, the fibrous by red arrows. The blue arrows indicate regions without retained morphology.

4 Conclusions

394 Two model alloys were subjected to a pearlite treatment fulfilling the Mn partitioning criterion only for
 395 α , but not for θ and therefore outside the established P-LE and NP-LE regimes. After the pearlite
 396 formation, an STA treatment was applied. With respect to the initial research questions, the following
 397 conclusions can be drawn:

- 398 • Even at low transformation temperatures and high Mn contents, a complete pearlite
 399 transformation is achieved with α and θ being the only constituting phases.
- 400 • Pearlite formation in the regime where the Mn partitioning condition is fulfilled only for α (and
 401 not for θ) still results in considerable Mn partitioning, indicating that partitioning occurs in a
 402 wider range of Mn and C contents as well as transformation temperatures than previously
 403 assessed in literature.
- 404 • It is likely that the low Mn equilibrium solubility of α is the decisive factor for the degree of
 405 partitioning between the two product phases. Thus, if the overall Mn content exceeds the
 406 solubility limit, noticeable Mn partitioning can be expected. However, if the C content and
 407 therefore the θ fraction is high, the degree of Mn partitioning might diminish.
- 408 • The chemical Mn pattern in both alloys is sufficiently strong to achieve the anticipated $\alpha' + \gamma$
 409 microstructure via STA from such pearlite. This provides independent proof of substantial Mn
 410 partitioning.

411 • The detailed analysis of experimental APT data on two Fe-Mn-C alloys, one with a low and
412 one with a high Mn content, suggests that the reaction cannot be described using the SCA-LE
413 method under the above conditions. The reconstructed tie lines do not share a common C iso-
414 activity in γ . Furthermore, the reaction does not follow conventional steady-state conditions, as
415 already indicated in Ref. [6]. Despite a quasi-steady-state growth for most of the reaction, the
416 pearlite inherits the overall alloy composition only with respect to the Mn content. The C
417 content may vary during growth, enabling a significant deviation of the phase fractions within
418 the quasi-steady-state regions compared to the predicted LE and GE values.

Data Availability Statement

419 The data presented in this study are available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17136940>
420 under CC BY-SA 4.0 license. The code including thermodynamic sample data is available here
421 <http://doi.org/10.35097/zxerv7gpadsje23a> under the same license. Further information is available upon
422 request with alexander.kauffmann@rub.de.

Declaration of Competing Interest

423 The authors declare that they have no competing interests or personal relationships that could have
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